

Table 1. Symptoms^a and plant height reduction at 30 and 60 d after infection in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV 7 d after soaking, Sep 1984, IRRI.

Variety	30 d after infection		60 d after infection	
	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)	Symptoms	Height reduction (%)
Sitopas	R ⁺⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	24	Tw, V	7
Ptb 18	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺ , V ⁺⁺	17
Tetep	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	29	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	22
Lemo	R ⁺ , Tw	57	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	36
Ptb 21	R ⁺ , Tw	59	V ⁺⁺	20
Utri Rajapan	R ⁺	52	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	21
Khao Mali	Tw	43	V ⁺⁺	21
Khao-Tah-Haeng	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	45	R ⁺⁺ , V ⁺	43
Kirikara	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺	68	R ⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	34
TN1	R ⁺ , V ⁺	56	R ⁺⁺ , Tw, V ⁺⁺	25

^aR = ragged leaves, Tw = twisted leaves, V = vein swelling. +, ++, +++ = degree of severity from low to high.

Table 2. Yield reduction in 10 rice varieties infected with RSV at different days after soaking, IRRI, Sep 1984.

Variety	Yield reduction (%)				
	7 DAS	15 DAS	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS
Sitopas	41	55	28	35	3
Ptb 18 ^a	38	65	28	21	-
Tetep	22	58	30	46	5
Lemo	57	-	33	-28	-21
Ptb 21	99	53	-10	-3	-22
Utri Rajapan	100	59	35	5	-39
Khao Mali	80	79	32	47	-16
Khao-Tah-Haeng	100	100	15	28	52
Kirikara	77	96	34	52	20
TN1	84	90	78	65	2

^a Percentage yield reduction was calculated based on the yield of plants inoculated at 60 DAS.

Tetep. The symptoms in plants infected at 30 DAS were milder and those in plants infected at 45 DAS were not clear in any varieties except Kirikara and TN1.

In the first trial, yield reduction was high in plants of almost all varieties infected at 7 or 15 DAS (Table 2). Sitopas, Ptb 18, Tetep, and Lemo have significantly less yield reduction than other varieties infected at the seedling stages. In the second trial, flowering was delayed and yield reduction was less than in the first trial in all varieties. Yield reduction in many varieties inoculated at 30 DAS was higher than in plants inoculated at 7 or 15 DAS. Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Ptb 21 had significantly lower yield reduction.

Sitopas, Ptb 18, Lemo, and Tetep developed milder symptoms and sustained less damage when infected with RSV at seedling stage. Their tolerance for RSV was due to their high ability to recover after severe infection at an early stage. □

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Incidence of rice kernel smut (KSm) in Pakistan

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Sixteen rice varieties were evaluated at Gujranwala and Sheikhpura district research farms against KSm by the partial vacuum method using the chlamyospores of *Tilletia barclayana*. Sporidial cultures were prepared on potato dextrose agar for inoculation of 20 panicles of each variety at anthesis. Percentages of infected panicles were recorded at maturity.

Varieties showed differential reaction at both locations. Disease incidence ranged from 5.25 to 95.25% at Sheikhpura and 6.25 to 97.25% at Gujranwala. C622 developed the lowest

Reaction of rice varieties to *Tilletia barclayana*. Islamabad, Pakistan.

Variety	Disease incidence (%)		Reaction
	Sheikhpura	Gujranwala	
Bara, Basmati Pak, Dokri Basmati, Jhona 349, Kangni, Melha 364, Motia, Mushakan, Palman, Ratria, Red rice, Sathra 278	>50	>50	Susceptible
Basmati 370, Sada gulab C622, IR579	>10 <10	>10 <10	Intermediate Resistant

infection, followed by IR579 and Basmati 370 (see table).

None of the varieties appeared to be immune. □

Reaction of selected varieties to tungro (RTV) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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Seven-day-old seedlings of ASD7, ARC11554, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Kataribhog, TKM6, TN1, and Utri Rajapan were individually exposed to one or five RTV-viruliferous adult

GLH. Longevity of adult GLH on the seedlings also was evaluated. Plants were scored 3 wk after inoculation for symptoms and assayed by latex test for the presence of the rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RSTV) viruses.

ARCI 1554, Gam Pai 30-12-15, Kataribhog, and Utri Rajapan showed low level of apparent RTV infection but were mostly infected with RTBV alone, regardless of the number of insects used for inoculation (see table). Average vector longevity was shorter on ARCI 1554 and Gam Pai 30-12-15, indicating resistance to GLH, and longer on Kataribhog and Utri Rajapan, indicating low resistance. TKM6 and ASD7 showed apparent RTV symptoms even when infected with RTBV.

Longevity of adult GLH, percentage of seedlings with apparent symptoms, and infection by RTBV and RTSV of rice varieties exposed to 1 or 5 RTV-viruliferous GLH. IRRI, 1987.

Variety	GLH longevity (d)	Seedlings infected ^a (%)							
		1 insect/seedling			5 insects/seedling				
		With apparent symptoms	By latex test			With apparent symptoms	By latex test		
RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV		RTSV	RTBV+ RTSV	RTBV		RTSV		
TN1	9.4	13	43	33	4	74	61	32	2
TKM6	1.3	47	0	48	0	39	3	46	0
Gam Pai 30-12-15	4.9	13	0	19	0	13	0	49	0
ASD7	3.8	33	7	38	4	46	25	47	2
Utri Rajapan	8.4	4	2	7	0	7	3	22	0
ARCI1554	4.1	0	0	11	0	11	0	22	0
Kataribhog	9.4	28	5	73	2	25	14	60	0

^aAv of 2 trials. Plants scored and assayed by latex test 3 wk after inoculation.

Kataribhog had low infection on the basis of symptoms but had high RTBV

infection, indicating symptomatic resistance (tolerance) to RTV. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Tolerance of some rice varieties for gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason

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Thirty-day-old seedlings of 15 varieties were transplanted singly at 15- × 15-cm spacing in two 18- × 3-m plots per entry

on 29 Jul 1982 to synchronize the vulnerable tillering stage with high GM infestation. The varieties were grown with 80 + 20 kg N, 18 kg P, and 33 kg K/ ha.

One plot of each variety was protected with granular diazinon applied to soil water at 1.50 kg ai/ha on 10, 25, and 40 d after transplanting (DT).

Because the experimental field tended to

be invaded by other insects (leaf folder, yellow borer, etc) from 40 DT, all plots were sprayed with 0.4 kg ai phosphamidon/ha at 40, 50, 60, and 70 DT.

Twelve 9-plant samples were marked at random in each plot. Percent silvershoots (SS) was estimated at 50 d after treatment and grain yields were recorded at harvest.

Vikram, PTB10, and CR94-MR1550

GM incidence and yield losses in some rice varieties. CRRI, Cuttack, 1982 wet season.

Variety	Seed to 50% flowering (d)	GM incidence (%)			Regression equation for expected yield (kg/ha)	Regression (r) value	% yield loss/unit % incidence	Reaction ^a to pest based on	
		Lowest	Highest	Mean (24 samples)				Incidence	Yield loss
GEB24	116	0	95	50	3161 - 19.6 ×	-0.747**	0.62	S	LT
Pankaj	113	10	91	46	1301 - 59.1 ×	-0.900**	0.81	S	LT
CR94R-MR1559	104	14	94	59	3119 - 34.1 ×	-0.699**	0.93	S	LT
Vijaya	96	17	93	54	4099 - 21.8 ×	-0.777**	0.68	S	LT
Sona	96	11	88	56	3321 - 11.3 ×	-0.802**	0.52	S	MT
Jaya	90	11	90	60	5913 - 55.2 ×	-0.887**	0.93	S	LT
CR58-MR1538	85	10	62	29	5658 - 62.6 ×	-0.747**	1.11	S	LT
Padma	82	18	91	49	2194 - 14.2 ×	-0.625**	0.51	S	MT
Bala	65	10	40	25	2405 - 23.5 ×	-0.450*	0.98	S	LT
Leuang 152	138	0	0	0	-	-	-	HR	-
Vikram	96	0	39	13	6072 - 32.2 ×	-0.282	0.53	R	-
CR94-MR1550	95	0	46	8	5588 - 28.0 ×	-0.215	0.50	R	-
PTB10	70	3	24	9	2112 - 1.6 ×	-0.151	0.35	R	-
CR1014	121	0	78	34	2569 + 1.3 ×	+0.342	-0.06	S	HT
Jagannath	113	0	80	35	4798 - 12.8 ×	-0.457*	0.27	S	HT

^aPercent silvershoots. S = susceptible, R = resistant, HR = highly resistant, LT = least tolerant, MT = moderately tolerant, HT = highly tolerant.